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Julia: The coin dating the Shroud – Extant of Tiberius Caesar as source in image transferred onto left-oculus of the Linen by quantum singularity

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Abstract

The authenticity of the Shroud of Turin (TS) – proving it a relic that dates to the First Century AD; specifically, what can be the linen cloth that wrapped the body of Jesus of Nazareth – may all be hinged on the identification of what appears to be coins over the eyes of the man whose image was transferred to the cloth, and consequently, the image of those objects that left an impression that suggests coins were used. The identification of any of these coins over the eyes is crucial in our understanding the nature of the Shroud and its plight theories surrounding it, and its applicability to science and para-science. Coins at the time of Jesus were struck with identifiable markings. The image of and/or name of a ruler, which may have included the year of reign, may have been among the features at the time such a coin was minted. The identification of the objects or protrusions that appear over the eye areas has lacked definitive support, remiss of a comprehensive study, single-source pattern interpretation, and devoid of the objects that caused such impressions on the cloth. Amid a plethora of shroud images and research tools, only a select may provide a workable basis or solution – substantiating further analysis. However, among the score of logs, volumes and images, there seems to be sufficient information available to carry out a reconstructing of what is the left-eye image on the Turin Shroud. What is more, the evidence points exclusively to an extant coin bearing the image of Julia, mother of the roman emperor, Tiberius Caesar who reigned during the years and ministry of Jesus of Nazareth. Moreover, the characteristics, i.e. surface and subsurface patterns on the coin that were transmitted to the linen fibers now rest in Shroud images; some of which were taken at the turn of the century. The original exposures and plates and their subsequent transfer to the current digital format, and the retention in their prime state qualities, are essentially, the optimum parameters in image analysis. Under the scope of rigorous scrutiny, the emerging patterns that show the etchings of what many in the Shroud community have long maintained.

Keywords: coins over the eyes, Turin Shroud, TS, dating the Shroud, Tiberius Caesar, ancient coins.

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1. Introduction

A reexamination of coins over the eyes

What some researchers have identified as objects or coins on the Shroud, a possibility that many have maintained over the past 4 decades, may in fact be exactly what these have for so long rightly speculated, within the lines, all along. Yet the finding may not come as a surprise on the heels of advancements in imaging software. J.F. Thackeray (2019) who supports the hypothesis that the left-eye could have been covered by an ancient coin, and is neither able to demonstrate his position, fashions a statement reflecting this consensus, adding further, the possibility has never been thrown out nor is able to be disproven. That which exists, not only displays the appearance of circular objects, but according to SEAM, they reflect a 3D quality about them. Thackeray notes,

Jumper et al (1978) suggested that two circular objects (apparently with a diameter of approximately 14 mm) were recognizable over the eyes of the person represented on the Shroud. It has been suggested by others (Filas 1982; Fontanille 2001; Whanger and Whanger 1985) that the objects might be coins. [...] Members of the Shroud of Turin Research Project (STURP) never denied that circular objects such as coins might be featured on the eyes of the person represented on the Shroud.

John Jackson and Eric Jumper, two PhD researchers working in the aerospace industry, using a computer called the VP8 Image Analyzer to study Shroud images, show in their research that the inherent properties in the Shroud consist of a combination of 3-dimensioning and brightness scale. They processed their results onto a mapped image as it appears on a screen monitor (SEAM, 2021). Peter S. Williams also notes Jackson and Jumper's subsequent opinion regarding the eye area: [they] "...observed the faint trace of objects placed over the eyes of the man in the Shroud, which they suggested might be coins (which would fit with First Century Jewish burial customs¹²)."

Despite contrasting opinion that the ancients did not maintain such practice, that reasoning may be dubious, when considering the alternative, that the only logical explanation¹, as to the presence of the coins as anomalies captured by the VP8 Image Analyzer, and the subsequent opinion of Jackson and Jumper. Other proponents in support of Jackson and Jumper's view were Francis Filas, a theological professor at Loyola University. Although Filas assimilated the objects represented the presence of coins, he specifically interpreted the right-eye image to be the imprint of a Pilate lepton, leaving the left-eye open for speculation (Filas, 1982).

It stands to reason, in consequential and objective order, that If these objects were circular, then, the possibility these may have been (I) **COINS** (Fig. 1). If these were in fact coins, these may have been used or (II) **CIRCULATED IN JESUS' TIME**. If these were used at the time of Jesus, then, they could bear (III) **IDENTIFIABLE MARKINGS**. And, finally, if these were coins that existed then, these may exist today and constitute an (IV) **EXTANT COIN**, that can be (A) **IDENTIFIED** as (B) **A MATCH**, having the (1) **SAME MARKING**, as it is the (2) **SAME COIN**. These follow an objective and reasonable order of logic.

In particularity to (III) *Identifiable markings*, the Tribute Penny (Fig. 1) on the obverse reads: "TI CAESAR DIVI AVG F AVGVST² ...," becoming identifiable as belonging to Tiberius Caesar the roman emperor who reigned during the time of Jesus. Thus, the design and inscription of the coin's underside is determinable, given the identification of the exposed side on the TS. Here, the reverse side (Fig. 2), bearing the partial of title: "PONTIF MAXIM³," as being observed in readable varieties of the same kind. The coin is dated to 18 AD, according to an industry source⁴.

Identifiable markings may constitute such stamping relative to its issuance, but by inclusion – flaws or patterns in the minting process, particular to the specimen in question (D.S. Barrett, 2000). Other considerations include certain subtleties common of the coin and the source images that may only be explained by the presence of the coin itself. Such plausible assumptions will be considered and remain the focus of this paper, as to why this coin is extant; ultimately, solving the monumental paradox in the dating of the TS.

¹ See: 'The Julia coin in a millennium milieu' (p9) for other information regarding the use of the coin in this research.

² Nomos auction 17, 26 October 2018 (102, #230).

³ Nomos – obolos 20, Lot 1068 (3 October 2021).

⁴ Classical Numismatics Group, LLC (CNG).

2. Method

Alongside visual templates

The identification of the left-eye coin on the Shroud would demand certain benchmarks to be met. In no particular order, a procedure would be established in reaching that determination. Initially, its purpose calls upon the use of at least one image of the TS related to the left-eye area, to obtain the visual information in comparing it to one of thousands of coins available today. It follows, to be fair and support those findings, and dispel further objections that may arise, it be prerequisite that the use of at least one other image, altogether of a different source and wholly independent of the first, would further support the results. However, this paper set out to be far more weighty and conclusive. Therefore, four other images were added, making use of the most critical of approaches. Namely, *affirming*, *confirming*, and *re-affirm* the process.

The resultant and correct coin, as discussed above, would be (A) **visually identifiable** (even as the TS images are naturally disturbed by weave patterns and electromagnetic qualities that may explain the forming of the image by quantum forces not yet fully grasped by science at this stage [even as exists enough information to establish the identification of the coin, remains]) by (1) **likeness in shape**, round or the like; and consisting of (2) **identifiable markings** on the coin's surface.

Understanding that due to the photo-radiation-like properties of the TS and of its spatial characteristics, images on the linen cloth may not appear in perfect uniformity, as these involve depth, light and shadow, electromagnetic properties, and the effects that these have on surface and subsurface⁵ imaging, in their positioning, in relation to the TS, when the image was imprinted. Nevertheless, their presence is apparent and has already been confirmed by many scholars and researchers.

Maintaining an impartial approach to the selective process is further advanced by the preponderance of the information that no two ancient coins bear the same similitudes or exactness, allowing the research to distinguish between specimens⁶. Thus, rather than introducing an exhaustive list of similar specimens to compare to the TS (which can unnecessarily divert from the purpose of this paper and burden our research – the legwork of which has expectedly been performed) thus shifting the sole focus on a unique type, in the research to identify the left-eye coin on the TS.

Various methods have been considered, going forward, in assessing if the 'Julia'⁷ coin would match the characteristics to those of the left-eye area of the TS. At the onset, the research for optimum quality images of the left-eye presented a challenge. Specifically, images become pixelated and distorted at the optical depth needed for proper photographic enhancements and analysis. Nevertheless, and for our purpose, some images were useful and ideal in this case.

The selection of the source images was based primarily on two criteria: 1) the image margins would have to extend out far enough to cover the coin's surface area; and 2) the image would display enough clarity to show enough details, whereby, certain patterns between these could serve to positively identify the coin, as the object (coin) that caused the actual imprint made on the left-eye on the TS. The exception to *criteria 1*, above, would be the use of the Fontanille image. Although, that particular image does not display as large an area to cover the entirety of the coin, it consists of enough detail, warranted by *criteria 2*, such as to be chosen as the 5th image in *this* analysis. Its prevalence and claim as a source in the identification of the left-eye image, serves as its own rebuttal in this paper.

To recapitulate the sources by order, meeting the above criteria: The Catalano image provided the clearest and most detail; the Enrie image proved useful in identification of certain patterns; the Vignon image displayed other subtleties, yet certain of these were detectable on the coin; the Castex image added to the nuanced patterns, while the Fontanille image constitutes the image left by the imprint of the Julia coin.

⁵ Furthering this view is Catalano M. (2017) in *The New Astonishing Phenomenon Detected on the Shroud* (p19); He states: "...the image [the Shroud image] is also similar to a radiograph, showing elements inside the body, as the stretch of the nail still inside the wrist of the left-hand..."

⁶ Kleiner FS (1978) (p5) [quoted: "...modern coining presses have three important advantages over the hammered method: the production of exactly circular blanks of uniform weight; the stamping of the blanks with clear, perfectly centered designs; and the marking of the edges of the coins with grooves or letters (or both) to insure against the reduction of a coin's metal content by filing."]

⁷ Julia is the name of the woman imaged on the reverse of the 'Tribute Penny.'

Figure 1: Bust of Tiberius Caesar – may unlock the dating dilemma to the TS—a mystery spanning the ages. A dark, dry substance present on the surface [neck, rim] is of speculation. Yet this side would have faced down over the eye of Jesus (Courtesy of Jonathan Schwartz)

Determining a best approach for comparing the images was another consideration, which, taken together, consisted of a geometric template with an outer concentric circle, boxed at the perimeter. The circle then divided and formed of 8 peripheral slices equally spaced along the perimeter. The configuration outlines the Julia coin on the left, comparing it to a source image on the right, to be proportional, thus ensuring a method by which images were properly sized to the coin's dimension⁸ and centered on the template.

The results should be indicative if the Julia coin will fit the thesis. With the initial method of measurement predetermined, the results of the surface patterns and markings of the Julia coin and the left-eye of the Turin Shroud can now be weighed, whether these validate the Julia coin theory. Although the comparisons in the following sections should be substantive enough to establish a link to the Julia coin, additional diagrams are provided in the exhibits.

⁸ For the analysis, the coin became the de facto working image. The Shroud, having the stretchable properties of a linen cloth, may be outside of axial proportionality, apparent in the stable properties intrinsic of the metal coin. Therein, the Shroud image was adjusted to properly sync to the coin's dimension.

Figure 2: Reverse showing Julia in regalia, mother of Caesar (Courtesy of Jonathan Schwartz⁹)

3. Pairing of images and analysis

The alongside comparative analysis in the form of an overlay slice mold and followed sequentially clockwise, reveals prominent features on the Julia coin are detectable on the source image (Fig. 4). These result in a range of more recognizable patterns or structures observable on the TS that correspond to the left-eye – to lesser, faint markings not captured optimally within the resolution parameters of the images; whereas the capturing of all subtleties, even in the true coin, would prove impossible, due to the nature of the TS linen and pixel limitations of image enhancement – To say, some of these are positively identified. These did not detract, however, from the scope of the findings, in assessing the identity of the Julia coin.

⁹ Fig. 1 and 2 show the original color images; although a grayscale version of the same is used throughout this Pape, to keep the visual aspect neutral and make pattern recognition more identifiable.

Figure 3: Redefining the boundaries of the Shroud of Turin (Courtesy of CNG)

The Julia coin in a millennium milieu

A historical precedence is necessitated to fit the emergence of the Julia coin theory. The basis for such would predispose that the protrusion seen over the left-eye of the TS, would, by requirement, not be any other form of object, but a coin – in fact, the coin itself. The coin, which existed during the time of Jesus, may have been in possession of Joseph of Arimathea, who is mentioned in the biblical account.¹⁰ In regards to the ancient practice of placing coins over the eyes, no reference is made in the biblical narrative. That idea has been proposed by the research of many a former contributor on the matter (Marino JG, 2021).

Historical evidence may support that artifacts that may have been associated with Jesus, may have, at one time, been regarded as sacred relics, and thus, handed down until the practice of such oral and/or written tradition, would have been lost to time or to the exclusion of such knowledge. That propensity waxed with the need to suppress that knowledge from the outside world, and may have further waned with the passage of time from generational awareness.

The ancient practice of safekeeping venerated relics may have been precisely selective, considering the ramifications of storing and wholly maintaining these, perhaps in reliquaries. Apparent to that practice, in most cases, no ancient inscriptions from the era made by their keepers have been found on the relics they guarded. With guided reason, such inscriptions would have placed these artifacts at peril of being discovered or taken over at the hands of marauders. The inscriptions, if made on these, would have also undermined the purity and sacredness they maintained. Careful consideration was given whether to write such accompanying markers, placing them with relics to hide them in an inconspicuous place.

Such an unlikely discovery may have occurred in 1492 at the Basilica of Santa Croce in Gerusalemme during a renovation. By certain accounts, the Titulus Crucis, believed to be the enigmatic overhead placard of the Cross bearing the title, 'Jesus of Nazareth, King of the Jews,' was found hidden in a keyhole within the roof. The relic was found inside a protective reliquary and an accompanying plaque was placed above with an inscription identifying its contents (Uten J, 1969). Varying arguments have been proposed regarding the timing of the discovery (van Eck MR, 2020); yet the very finding may hold truth to it, as it maintains characteristics significant of what the church considered sacrosanct; namely: 1) a relic hidden from view; 2) in an unlikely place; 3) inside a holy place – a basilica; and 4) with an identifying plaque of the contents within the reliquary.

In regards to the Julia coin and its precedence at the Resurrection, the small coin, which may have been found inside the empty tomb – it may or not have been clear to those who later entered the tomb, its purpose – the covering of the left-eye. Yet time and again, the Shroud provides an untainted photo-negative of its existence, captured by the images of the linen's surface that remain unmistakable of its identification on record.

¹⁰ Matthew 27:57; taken from Lanny Mebust's translation of the New Testament.

Figure 4: Catalano source image showing unmatched detail – used in the analysis of the Julia coin; the color was adjusted to produce a grayscale to achieve visual enhancement (Source: G.M. Catalano*)

* See: Section 6 for source details.

3.1 On the Catalano image

The source image (Fig. 4) serves in the initial comparison. For the purpose of this section, two flowcharts symbols (y, o) were superimposed to further divide the image into corresponding parts. What follows is the subdivision of the image into 8 equal parts or slices, each with a description of what can be identified as markings or patterns, with those that may be noted on the coin.

Slice-1: Visible above the head of the empress and forming at the ridge of the coin, a gladiator's helmet or *m* shape. The shape extends to slice-8 as seen in the image. Appearing is a type of lighting effect that casts a shadow from left to right on the image. A bulge is detected as the cause of this shadowing effect. The presence of Julia's headdress is detected about $\frac{3}{5}$ th the vertical length of the slice, forming a burnished spot. Beneath it, a diagonal line traversing slice-8, the neck area, and into Julia's bust, detectable as two protrusions or as dark spot formations.

Slice-2: The presence of circular patterns. Certain ridges on the coin may be detected on the image, i.e. a diagonal ridge that is created, what appears to be by the holding of a palm or olive branch with Julia's right-hand; this creates a ridge, mound-shape visible on both images as seen (Fig. 5).

Slice-3: V pattern, left of the letters P-O-N, forming an outline.

Slice-4: A vertical pattern identifies as the front leg of the seat of power. The structure coincides with the height on the coin, terminating at the top of the slice where the perimeter of slice-4 (red line) runs down from the center at a diagonal 45°; beneath the pattern, at a slight placement to the left, a nose-like structure, the base of the formation (bottom of what appear as nostrils) match the vertical and horizontal layout on the coin and the image.

3.1.1 Anatomical nose structure

Linking to the coin in the source image, a recognizable and obvious anomaly dominates at the 6 o'clock bottom side of the Julia coin. No reason is known or can be suggested why the image bears in resemblance to the shape of a human nose. The image showing what seems to resemble a pair of anatomic nostrils and it suggests a magnetic-radioactive 'phenomenon' (Catalano GM, 2017) occurred that resulted in its imprinting on the TS linen cloth. The event, as captured, triggered an atomic response in objects found at close proximity to the cloth, whereby different quantum levels affected gave off photo-electric bursts resulting in an image that appears clustered beyond the mere recognizable surface (unexplainably, dark areas on the image show bleed-through from beneath the surface of the coin, as a result). The observed image showing subsurface patterns results, yet its relative axial position, e.g. x and y, is evidenced by its location on the coin. The anomaly, as it appears, is reconfirmed by a second set of nostrils that appear as a surface structure on the Julia coin just below the upper set that appear on the Catalano image; although the former appears only slightly on the coin as traces.

From a theological ascription, albeit symbolism related to the creation account, the nostrils can be a pictogram for when God breathed life into the nostrils of Adam, the first man He created out of dust. It may be noted that those who placed the coin over the left-eye of Jesus, might have regarded sacred symbolism and perhaps attributed certain features on coins to be emblematic or iconic of their deep-rooted spiritual beliefs. But beyond speculation, many apparent characteristics have become obvious of the Julia coin with the source images, to be regarded as a historical object that best resolves the coin-over-the-eyes conflict.

Slice-5: A line runs vertically $\frac{3}{5}$ th along the top of the slice; the same area shows the rear leg of the seat of power on the coin; a vertical is detectable terminating in slice-8. This appears as the staff of Julia on the coin.

Slice-6: Faint tracing of the letters *I* and *M*.

Slice-7: Line patterns appearing on the Catalano image appear on the coin.

Slice-8: Diagonal lines; circles; the top of Julia's staff.

Slice-4 – 8:

3.1.2 Border etching pattern

An identifiable border runs the gamut in relative distance to the rim on the coin. A broken or dotted pattern is detected on the coin following in counter-clockwise fashion along the left side of the coin terminating about the footrest of Julia. The alongside to the Catalano image (Fig. 5) identifies the pattern equidistant to the left edge of the coin. Ancient coins of this type were unique in striking. As such, no two coins were struck identical. In contrast to a solid continuous border, a broken or dotted edging appears in detectable arrangement. Furthermore, the dots appear equal in size and equidistant, such that these correspond visually to the coin. The border is sequentially absent in the space starting at the 12 o'clock position (slice-1) above the head of Julia, terminating approximately at the 4 o'clock position (slice-3).

Figure 5: The Schwartz (Julia coin) and Catalano source images were paired using an octal slice overlay template to compare the images. Here, the images are shown in grayscale; the intended focus was to shift from color, to more recognizable patterns, textures, and shades between the images (Sources: Jonathan Schwartz; G.M. Catalano)

Images are as accurately scaled and paired by A Lerma.

Figure 6: Enrie source image – the monochromatic photograph of the TS showing a different resolution, including additional details uniquely captured of the TS and in the weighing of the evidence of the Julia coin theory (Source: Mario Latendresse/Shroudscope.com*)

* See: Section 6 for source details.

3.2 On the ShroudScope Enrie image

A second source image proves invaluable, showing the characteristics between it and the Julia coin. The initial photograph taken in 1931 by Giuseppe Enrie shows various patterns that are consistent with those found on the surface of the Julia coin.

The pervasiveness of the Enrie image has been idealized in their own unique sense by those who offer divergent opinions on the left-eye area. The overlap made by certain estimates relate in background to the Julia coin in the way and description thereof:

...Left-eye area on Enrie negative sepia photograph of the Shroud. As can be seen (when enlarged), there may be a design on the object over the left-eye [...] Nevertheless, Filas on the evidence of three short curving lines that spread away from each other, on an enlargement of a 1931 Enrie photograph of the Shroud face, suggested that the object over the left-eye was also a Pontius Pilate coin known as the Julia lepton [...] As can be seen above a vertical and a horizontal line cross over the left-eye. The horizontal line is a fold in the cloth and the vertical line is a prominent thread. (Jones SE, 2020)

Several observations can be made regarding Jones, in the above. Jones agrees that there is something actually visible, although he only suggests later it may be a lepton and this according to Filas. What is significant is that during Jesus' time coins were issued as a tribute to Julia who held sway over the Roman Empire with Tiberius, her son. Yet these statements have not been held with complete certainty, allowing only for fancy of speculation, at best. Finally, Jones references Moroni regarding the horizontal and vertical lines found over the left-eye. Be these folds or prominent treads, these cross over at Julia's girdle which may have caused pleating on the linen of the Shroud.

3.2.1 Emblazoned headdress

The detail in the monochromatic (black and white) image (Fig. 7) further supports the Julia left-eye-coin theory. The head regalia of Julia, empress of Rome displays at the top middle portion on the template. The head is correctly positioned at 90 degrees on the Enrie image and justifiably in line with a vertical intention. The head appearing in a top-down position in line with the backrest of the royal throne reveals attention to detail and purposeful placement of the Julia coin, in upright fashion, over the left-eye. Note its location at $3/5^{\text{th}}$ vertical distance from the bottom of slice-1. A bright and shiny protuberance denotes what is likewise an observable feature on the Julia coin. This is found in a precise position located at the center of Julia's headdress. A triangle-top pattern forms just above the brow of Julia and angles down the sides – the left side following the outline of her headdress – the pattern is observable on the coin. The bust is traceable on the coin per the layout of the template.

Slice-2: At the bottom left in close approximation to the center of the template is found what appears to be a bulge with lines that intersect in a cross pattern at the location. The location on the coin template denotes that a prominent feature is the cause of the anomaly. Its location marks the place where Julia's girdle creates the protuberance seen on the Enrie image. At the top of the slice, a boomerang form with a bulging center appears on the Enrie; note the texture and similarity of the shape on the coin.

Slice-3: At the bottom a glazed pattern appears and is similar to an A shape. The pattern trails-off the circular template. At the top, the shape curves downward and left. The coin template reveals that the curvature follows a pattern close to the coin's perimeter, giving it the radial form.

Slice-4: At the left, the vertical streak that traverses Julia's girdle runs downward in line with the front leg of Julia's seat of power as is depicted on the coin. Breaks and formations on the vertical streak run relative to the adornments seen on the front leg on the Julia coin.

Slice-5: In proximity to the center, the shape of a skewed A is present on the image. The pattern is not as defined on the coin although the texture and formation regarding the same location appears to be the cause.

Slice-6: Appearing at the lower left of the image, a shapely-styled, capitalized E is set at an approximate 45° inclination. The placement synchronizes with the lower left perimeter of the Julia coin, where the backside of the E delineates the edge of the coin.

Slice-7: Various formations, more defined on the Enrie image appear as well on the coin; although no particular strong points can be made from these, certain of such patterns comprise of an A formation at the right of the slice, and a pattern running across the major bottom half of the slice similar in resemblance to a pair of joined boots pointed upwards.

Slice-8: A streaked outline at top left depicts the perimeter of the Julia coin. Note the outline is faintly visible, stretching down slightly, showing the coins perimeter on the Enrie image.

Figure 7: This side comparison between the Schwartz and Enrie images may show certain patterns are more pronounced on certain photographs like the Enrie image. Perhaps the most prominent of these is what is already visible on the Julia coin. Other similitudes include the circular form about the left perimeter (Sources: Jonathan Schwartz; Mario Latendresse/ShroudScope.com)

Images are as accurately scaled and paired by A Lerma.

Figure 8: Vignon source image – showing other subtleties not captured by the initial source images; thus used as an additional source for detecting the presence of the Julia coin (Source: Vignon P*)

* See: Section 6 for source details.

3.3 On the Vignon image

The Vignon image is altogether of a unique exposure that captures certain characteristics of the Schwartz image, the Julia coin – where the other source images show their own particular patterns of the eye area. Here, the image is shown in a grayscale version to provide a more neutral observation whereby the natural image color was avoided and thereby any minimal tendency, where even the natural color may mislead the judgement of the forms or shapes that may be observed on the image. Both on the original Vignon and grayscale version the center appears darker and seems to follow a radial form that suggests it follows in the presence of a circular shape object in the image-to-Shroud transfer.

The significant opinion mentioning the use of the Vignon image was shared in a related posting in regards to the coins over the eyes of the man on the Shroud:

... All photos of the Shroud make their own enhancements to the original [...] The Enrie 1931 sepia print that I scanned from Vignon's "Le Saint Suaire de Turin" is claimed to be one of the best photographs for showing the coin details [...] early coins like leptons don't have a raised edge and the image of the coins over the eyes of the man on the Shroud came off the high points... (Jones SE, 2013)

Firstly, Jones correctly notes that every photo that is taken from the Shroud comprises its own unique characteristics of what it captures on the Shroud. He gives credence to the quality of the Vignon image that is here used as the 3rd of 5 source images in this paper. Thirdly, Jones points out that “leptons don’t have a raised edge.” As has already been shown on the Catalano image, a raised border running along the left side on the reverse of the Julia coin – what is supposed to be an off-center border struck error – confirms the absence of the former coin in this region, while denoting the latter. And, lastly, again, he concludes that these are in fact coins since they “came off the high points,” meaning they appear as raised objects over the eyes and in close approximation to the linen sheet that likely caused their image to leave a denser imprint.

Slice-1: A ridge runs vertical to the left side of the slice. It may be observed that the ridge in the Vignon image is of a lighter color, where the same may be seen on the coin over Julia’s head shows a darker contrast. Note also that near the top of the coin that the formation split-ends into the shape of an *m*, mimicking the shape of a gladiator helmet where the eyes are not covered but are exposed. This effect is likewise observed on the Julia coin. The general shape on the images creates it, thus two eye sockets are seen, even as these are only the perception following the formation.

Slice-2: At Julia’s girdle, a prominent bulge is found where a pair formation consisting of a vertical and horizontal streak intersects just above Julia’s lap.

Slice-3: At roughly 4/5^{ths} the vertical distance to the top of the slice and located at the perimeter of the coin, note a bubbled anomaly may be seen on the coin. The same may be observed on the Vignon image at precisely the corresponding place. Note other formations appearing on both.

Slice-4: A vertical streak runs parallel, in back of the front leg of Julia’s seat of power. The image is cut off at the bottom, making the observation limited.

Slice-5: The presence of a corresponding vertical streak on the Vignon follows the outline of Julia’s staff as depicted on the Julia coin.

Slice-6: A dark spot on the right side of the slice on the left side of the staff shows up as a bubble formation on the Vignon image.

Slice-7: A similar formation as found in slice-1 is noticeable on the lower right side of the slice. The formation bears in resemblance to the gladiator’s helmet where the eyes are exposed. The right side is more challenging to visualize on the Julia coin; whereas the left arch may be followed and is more visually apparent on the coin. The outline of Julia’s staff is likewise traceable on the Vignon image.

Slice-8: The distinct anomaly of the shape of a human head appears at about the middle right side of the slice. The head appears facing right to the back of Julia’s headdress; the observable nose is precisely vertically in line between the bun and top of the head of the headdress; the hairline of the image and the texture on the Vignon may require of slightly keen observation, nonetheless, the pattern is noted at the precise location on the Julia coin; the folding right hand of Julia is detectable on the Vignon image as a dark form and outline. Note the two lumps that appear horizontally side by side at about the middle left side on the Vignon image. These may be traced to slightly noticeable areas; namely, left of Julia’s right-elbow, and at the intersection of her arm and the staff that she is holding; an *A* appearing on the left corner of the Vignon image; the assimilation pertains to the coin where the *A* is formed partly by the coin’s edge.

Figure 9: At right, the border of the Vignon image comes short of the template edge. A comparison with other images like the Enrie and Castex were the initial basis for aligning the Vignon image to the template; a final consideration would require its layout align to the coin itself (Sources: Jonathan Schwartz; Vignon P)

Images are as accurately scaled and paired by A Lerma.

Figure 10: Castex source image – weighs in on the Julia coin theory, providing additional clues to the identity of the coin; the image bears in resemblance to the Enrie photograph, maintaining pattern information, characteristically unique (Source: Thierry Castex*)

* See: Section 6 for source details.

3.4 On the Castex¹¹ image

The initial observation of the image, although resembling particularly in likeness to the Enrie photograph, it casts the TS region under its own scope and parameters that differentiate enough from it; yet the image being of a more nebulous appearance such that the lens focuses on subtleties not captured by the Enrie or other source images that were used particularly in the same.

Slice-1: The shape of a backward-resting A-form is observed at the top left of the slice, over Julia's headdress, visible on the source image; the shape is less apparent on the coin, yet carefully observed following the chalky lines that form the same shape; two bulge anomalies characteristic of bubbles appear on the middle left of the slice, the lower of these is traced to the neck-chin area on the coin. Observe the boomeranged A shape forming above this bubble on the source image, is defined on the coin as a traceable outline of the headdress shape where the top of the A pattern peaks above the brow, as is observed on the coin.

Slice-2: At the bottom lower left, A swell at the center of a cross pattern aligns with Julia's girdle on the coin where the convergence of a raised pattern meets at the precise point. Note the location rests just above the horizontal crosshairs of the template on both images.

Slice-3: Two shapes are located side-by-side; these take the form of bubble formations and are found to be in vertical relation to Julia's right-ankle; although these are more easily observed on the source image, their shape apparently emanates from the subsurface of the coin, keenly seen on the coin's surface.

Slice-4: A shape that appears as a horseshoe or *n* is observed on the source image near the bottom right. A comparison of the same area on the coin shows an obvious pattern derives; the right side of the shape, on the coin, conforms to the same angle of a line formation running parallel with the diagonal crosshairs of the template; the same horseshoe can be traced out on the coin area where line patterns form the shape.

Slice-5: Three bulges are visible on the upper section of the slice and may be observed on the source image. The lower of these syncs precisely with the bottom of a v-form, an adorning accent on the rear leg of the seat of power; the middle may be observed to the left of the staff, while the topmost placement is set on the location where the top of the hind leg and the back of the seat meet.

Slice-6: An 8 pattern forms atop of the slice slightly left of the middle. The top dark center of the upper half of the pattern corresponds to the location of the top of the letter *I* on the coin; the lower dark section of the pattern is attributable to a bulge anomaly located at the first peak of the letter *M* on the coin.

Slice-7: A dark shaded spot near the top of the slice may be seen on the source image; the same area corresponds to a location left (bottom) of the *M* where lines of the letter converge and form a bulge. To the right and slightly lower of this appears the shape of an *S* that takes up the greater middle area of the slice. The similarity of the pattern can be made out on the surface of the coin.

Slice-8: It can be observed on the coin's surface that the headdress of Julia in slice-1 appears as a shadowed¹² or repeated image in slice-8. With a careful eye to the intricacy of detail on the surface, such features as the bun and headdress reappear about 1 cm to the left and slightly higher at a 45° angle of the original stamped image. The anomaly is characteristic of an event horizon, essentially, a release of energy at the molecular level by a force or catalyst that may be beyond the scope of science or at the fringes of our own understanding.

The meshed image (Supplement D-5) further supports the patterns and anomalies found in the slice sections of Figure 11 configured by the imaging template, i.e. Julia's headdress is an observable formation pattern. The inclusion of the meshed or checkered image of the Julia coin with the source image further supports the image template via the vertical and horizontal approach vs. slice patterns.

¹¹ The source underscores the use of a "Non-destructive processing of the Holy Shroud image" and the application of filters to remove weave patterns from the Enrie image to obtain a crisper and clearer image of the face on the Shroud which includes the eye areas. Fig. 2 in the article shows the usage of such a process with the results consisting of the before-and-after images minus the filtering of the present weave patterns. Although the process used by Thierry Castex successfully rids the unwanted background patterns intrinsic in the Enrie image, it does so at the cost of sacrificing valuable image sharpness, causing the details surrounding the eye areas to become more obscure and more a challenge to compare the Julia coin to. Therefore, the original pre-filtered image that was used in the article, "Etude de l'image du Linceul de Turinwas" was considered to be the more suitable of the two and also served as the preferred source image in this Pape.

¹² A similar view is shared by Catalano GM (2017) in The New Astonishing Phenomenon Detected on the Shroud (p19); He states: "If a source of energy radiates spherical waves across an object, like in radiography, the image obtained on the projection surface is the **shadow** of the more or less transparent matter the waves passed through." [Emphasis added]

Figure 11: The Castex image showing visual similarities to photographs like the Enrie. These formations include Julia's headdress, the intersecting vertical and horizontal lines at her girdle, a styled *E* in slice-5, and what resembles a boot pattern in slice-7
(Sources: Jonathan Schwartz; Thierry Castex)

Images are as accurately scaled and paired by A Lerma.

3.5 On the segmented Fontanille image

A final source was considered in obtaining further image sampling, adding to the relevancy of the identifying markings on the left-eye of the TS. The source Image¹³ is the result of his work, as illustrated by Jean-Phillipe Fontanille, a numismatic expert in 1978, regarding the coin on the left-eye. Fontanille identifies what he postulates is the left-eye coin as being a Pilate coin. However, lacking are sufficient results with no other supporting images and other considerations not being comprehended within his findings. These images are limited in range and cover only a portion of the left-eye, leaving the macro out of view. The inclusion of the Fontanille image, as a result, required overlay on a larger image, to illustrate its proportions, as compared to the left-eye area on the TS¹⁴.

Figure 12 captures the Fontanille image, illustrating its dimensional properties being at one-quarter the size of the Julia coin, whose image, coincidentally, may be framed, positioned over Julia's seat of power; in no such way preconceived as a fated image on her lap. The alongside image (Fig. 12) used the Schwartz and Vignon images as the backdrops to the Fontanille. The intended purpose was to show the continuation patterns of the linen fibers onto contrasting backgrounds.

The correct positioning of the Fontanille image over the Vignon and Schwartz images can be confirmed, particularly, by the observance of patterns on the overlay image correctly align with the backdrop. The slightest of misalignments would expose a break and inconsistency in the texture or pattern visible; yet alignment is maintained around the square area where the Fontanille image meshes with the surrounding backdrop. To further facilitate pattern recognition, the original Fontanille image was enhanced, where the grayscale of backdrop images were used; thus providing a contrast to assist in identifying of the same – patterns or textures. The effect is seen here where the Fontanille is distinct from the Schwartz and Vignon images¹⁵.

Some identifiable patterns are observable, although, considering the limited scope of the Fontanille image; it confirms the significance of the previous source images. Generally, patterns shared between the Schwartz/Fontanille and Vignon/Fontanille images maintain a fluid continuity. The observability of breaks or misalignments between the images may not be apparent or identifiable. Despite the limitation due in part to the caption 'Enhanced¹⁶,' the overlay suggests that the images are properly in alignment and in sync, even as the Schwartz is synchronized to the Vignon image and the Fontanille, in turn, to each of these.

On the left, the backrest of Julia meets the Fontanille image (lower, left side), where dark lines of the grayscale backdrop continue onto the colored Fontanille. Two of these line patterns are easily observable, while other line formations, below these, may be seen as continuing forms between the two. Other observations regarding the superimposed image on the left are more subtle, yet not indistinguishable. Various patterns traverse the Fontanille image in more-or-less a horizontal direction. On the Fontanille, a ridge follows across the upper top, at approximately shoulder level to Julia, terminating at about 3/4th the verticals distance on the right of the image.

The observations of the left image would imply that a certain alignment would be maintained on the right images between the Vignon and Fontanille. In the case of the Vignon image, the contrast of this darker background allows a different observation to be had, including the comparison of weave patterns visible on the textured backdrop. Patterns that were more apparent on the left image are altogether, even non-observable on the right layout. The different backdrop that pertains to the linen fibers of the TS is unique to the metallic surface of the Julia coin; thus patterns may not be observed in one, yet in the other.

Running in approximation at the middle of the Fontanille on the right image, a ripple is strewn at about a halfway point and stretches out to the right, where it continues onto the backdrop of the Vignon image. The texture, width, shading and direction are carried beyond the Fontanille border. Other observations may be made.

¹³ Refer to Supplement A (p30) for additional supporting images.

¹⁴ This resulted in the superimposing of the Fontanille on the Vignon image inclusive for this purpose. The challenge comprised in the resizing and centering of both images to achieve an accurate representation for the scope of the work required in obtaining par excellence results. The resultant image (Fig. 12) was then used as a scaled working model between *it* and the Julia coin to include the work of Jean-Phillipe Fontanille and to resolve the identity of the coin that he initially proposed to be a Pilate coin. The results of the findings would be limited by the visual information obtainable in slice-4 through -8, due to the dimensions of the Fontanille image within the left-eye area scope. The information linking any observable patterns or markings was then rendered in the concluding observations.

¹⁵ Fig. 12 – the Schwartz/Fontanille and Vignon/Fontanille images were intentionally contrasted (grayscale exposed and color enhanced, respectively), to help identify surface pattern continuity. Note pattern follow-through may be vertical, horizontal, or diagonal.

¹⁶ The word 'Enhanced' appears on the image of Jean-Philippe Fontanille covering the left-eye area of the Shroud.

Figure 12: The use of a 5th source provided an auxiliary angle at this juncture of the visual-technical process. Here, the Fontanille image was superimposed using a grayscale background to contrast with the color scheme of the Fontanille source; this in providing keen observation in distinguishing line patterns and textures, as they formed at the perimeter of the image – showing if continuity of patterns existed at the edges (Sources: Schwartz; Vignon; Fontanille)

Images are as accurately scaled and paired by A Lerma.

4. Discussion: The exclusivity of Julia

Based on the results, the findings suggest that the Julia coin could only have been the coin whose image was caused to become imprinted on the left-eye of the TS. Several reasons in reaching this determination were considered, weighed for substance of evidence. Basing on the coin's historical context, religious significance, and modern imaging analysis, these key areas formed the basis in the interpretation of the findings in this paper.

4.1 Validation of sources¹⁷

While the use of one source to determine the coin's identity (if it is a match) may yield enough detail in the gathering of the data and results – or may arguably be insufficient for its purpose, this paper added not only a secondary source but five wholly independent source images to dispel any bias in the findings. The Catalano and Enrie image were initially used to compare the coin to the left-eye area of the TS. Yet the availability of the Vignon and Castex Images added two additional layers of data that served in the identification of the Julia coin. The unique characteristics of each source image helped to expose the coin's details only visible and native to that image and further confirming the identity of the Julia coin. The first image provided an overall supporting match, adding clarity in comparing the features of the Julia coin to the Shroud. In the second image, it is Julia's headdress visible at the top center that further maintains the identity of the coin. The third image shows a head form behind Julia's headdress and an identifiable radial rim outline. The fourth image is characteristically unique in scope and Enrie-like in style; importantly exposes patterns on the coin and further supports that these stem from the Julia coin. Finally, in a fifth image, although not entirely considered a full source image, does serve and dispels any final bias and adequately reveals the true coin behind Jean-Philippe Fontanille's left-eye-coin theory.

4.2 Unique striking

Ancient coins followed a selective minting process. Coins were struck in a unique way. The practice of striking a coin was not uniform, and as a result, coins differed in shape and pattern markings that were unique to the coin's makeup. This, in turn, made the coin's features identifiable and different from similar coins. D.S. Barrett underscores the degree of variance in coin stamping:

With the simplest arrangement for striking, as illustrated, a mint worker found it very difficult to achieve axial coordination between the obverse and the reverse of his coins; that is the design on one side would most likely be along a different axis from that on the other side. Off-centre striking was also prevalent. [...] On the other hand, while modern mints have obviated such technical problems, the perfection of their coins frequently appears sterile in contrast to the lively **individuality of ancient coins**. [Emphasis added]

As such, these coins still bear the same surface pattern (discounting wear or damage) on them. In regard to the Julia coin, a stamped border runs from atop Julia's head to about her footrest, roughly at 4 o'clock. This flaw in the coin is observable on the TS. This with other, i.e. Julia's head placement, anatomical nose image, and other features being unique to the coin and are further evidenced by the supporting images.

4.3 Historical context

The inclusion of the Julia coin as it was placed over the left-eye would have to make sense and fit the historical context, if and in fact a coin was actually placed there. We would rule out all coin issues made after the time of Jesus, if we were attempting to prove that the TS is of Jesus and/or whose image was formed during the era in which he lived. Thereby it is conceivable and not unreasonable of the Julia coin whose obverse shows the image of Tiberius Caesar. Tiberius who reigned as emperor of Rome from AD14 to AD37 and whose coins were in circulation, was in fact the emperor of Rome at the time of Jesus. Although the historical context does not specifically identify any particular coin as the one that is suggested in this paper, it does presuppose a date of the coin that does not exceed the time of Jesus, and the Julia coin fits the requirement. .

4.4 An artifact passed down

In the Gospel narrative, Joseph of Arimathea is identified as a pious, noble and a rich man. It is him and Nicodemus, a Pharisee who care for Jesus' body after the Crucifixion. According to sources, it is Joseph who offers

¹⁷ Sources: (1) G.M. Catalano; (2) Enrie image (Mario Latendresse/ShroudScope website); (3) Vignon P; (4) Castex T; (5) J-P Fontanille.

to place Jesus' body in a tomb that he had hewn for himself. The Gospel mentions Joseph as a disciple of Jesus. If Joseph, a Jew, believed that Jesus was the expected Messiah that had fulfilled biblical prophecy by dying on the Cross, this view would be evidenced and supported by the actions that he took immediately following the Crucifixion by asking Pilate, the procurator of Judea for the body of Jesus (Lerma A, 2024). Sources confirm that Jesus was entombed in a way only noble to that of a king (Bevilacqua M, Fanti G, D'Arienzo M, 2017). Joseph would have been able to carry out an expensive preparation at the time as is evidenced by the aloes and spices that were used as recounted in the Gospels. If Joseph placed coins over the eyes of Jesus, these same might have taken on a deeper religious significance and turned into relics only after it was believed Jesus resurrected from the tomb. With such an event, perhaps Joseph's faith might have deepened and more resolved in believing that Jesus was in fact the Messiah. As Joseph was the owner of the tomb, he also might have considered the entire site holy after the Resurrection event, even perhaps ascribing religious value to everything inside the tomb. And if coins were used he might have valued them as relics post-Resurrection. Thereby these would have been kept safe whether inside the tomb or in a special reliquary elsewhere; even placing them in the care and keep of the next generation after him. In any event, even if these coins were at one point regarded as relics, it would seem probable that their significance might have been lost to time by the sharing of information in generational awareness circles. This would lead to the formation of a supporting hypothesis that the coin that was attributed as having a place in the Resurrection had safe-keeping perhaps for centuries being held sacred until its meaning might have become lost with the passage of time.

5. Conclusion: The case for Julia

The analysis of the Julia coin and its implication is far-reaching. The research builds upon over 40 years of groundwork laid by researchers who suggested the presence of circular objects over the man whose image left an imprint on the Shroud. This includes the work of Jackson and Jumper who with the aid of the VP-8 Image Analyzer were able to make *that* determination (Jones SE, 2020). Moreover, these circular patterns show their form in the source images that were used to show the similarities stem from the Julia coin. In every image that was used, a unique set of characteristics showed traits that may only be exhibited by the presence of the coin. It suggests this impression resulted from photo-static particles that came in contact with the Shroud linen.

Based on systemic image analysis of five source images and lacking a more feasible argument to explain how a plethora of patterns match with those of the Julia coin, the indicators suggest the presence of the Julia coin's reverse as the source of the imprint on the left-eye of the Shroud – all other factors weighed.

6. References, copyrights & attributions

Acknowledgement

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Additional supplementary information

Please refer to Supplements A-F for additional diagrams and tables on the Schwartz and source images used in the preceding sections. The 'References' page also provides additional sources and information. Finally, some resourceful websites covering this and other topics are Shroud.com and ShroudofTurinGuild.org, among others.

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Figures 1 and 2: The image of the Tiberius coin is courtesy of Schwartz, Jonathan. "Roman Tiberius AR Denarius Silver Tribute Penny Coin 14-37 AD – Good VF / XF".

Photograph. 2022. EBay.

<https://www.ebay.com/itm/185068008719>

(Retrieved September 28, 2022)

Figure 3: The obverse and reverse of the coin is courtesy of Classical Numismatics Group, LLC. "Tiberius. AD 1f4-37. AR Denarius (19mm, 3.73g, 2h). "Tribute Penny" type. Lugdunum (Lyon) mint. Group 3, AD 18"; Photograph. 2021, CNG

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Figure 4: The Catalano image is the left-eye area of the Shroud of Turin. The image is cropped and visually enhanced. The image is attributable to G.M. Catalano, "The New Astonishing Phenomenon Detected on the Shroud" from the International Institute for Advanced Studies of Space Representation Science in Palermo, Italy.

Figure 5: Pairing of Schwartz/Catalano images using an octagonal template. The images are enhanced and are attributable to Jonathan Schwartz and G.M. Catalano.

Figure 6: The image is the left-eye area of the Shroud of Turin from the Enrie photograph. The image is cropped and visually enhanced and is attributable to Mario Latendresse and ShroudScope at the Sindonology Web site,

<https://dShroud.com/ShroudScope/ShroudScope.shtml> (Site accessed 2023)

Figure 7: Pairing of Schwartz/Enrie images using an octagonal template. The images are enhanced and are attributable to Jonathan Schwartz and Mario Latendresse and the ShroudScope website.

Figure 8: The image is the left-eye area of the Shroud of Turin from the Vignon image. The image is cropped and visually enhanced.

Vignon, P., 1902, "The Shroud of Christ," University Books: New York NY, Reprinted, 1970, p.137; de Wesselow, T., 2012, "The Sign: The Shroud of Turin and the Secret of the Resurrection," Viking: London, pp.100-101.

Figure 9: Pairing of Schwartz/Vignon images using an octagonal template. The images are enhanced and are attributable to Jonathan Schwartz and Vignon P.

Figure 10: The image is the left-eye area of the Shroud of Turin from the Castex image. The image is cropped and visually enhanced and is attributable to Thierry Castex.

Figure 11: Pairing of Schwartz/Castex images using an octagonal template. The images are enhanced and are attributable to Jonathan Schwartz and Thierry Castex.

Figure 12: Pairing of Schwartz/Vignon images using an octagonal template. These are used as a background for superimposing the Fontanille image; the images are enhanced and are attributable to Jonathan Schwartz, Vignon P, and Jean-Phillipe Fontanille. The following is cited as the source for the latter: Fontanille, J-P (2001) "The Coins of Pontius Pilate," Shangri-La Publications: Ithaca NY, in "The Coinage Evidence", The Holy Shroud of Turin, 7 May 2010

Supplement A: Block segment comparison of three images and pattern analysis

Supplement B1-B4: Letter mapping of source images, transfer from the Julia coin

Supplement C1-C2: Defined markings in and around the lettering vicinity

Supplement D1-D5: Checkbox template of source images with two observations

Supplement E1-E4: Cross-hash mapping using the Julia coin's points of reference

Supplement F: Course of linen fibers determined by a unique Vignon image

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Schwartz/ Fontanille/Vignon segment match

Supplement A

Some images are cropped and resized to scale; the Schwartz, Fontanille, and Vignon images are shown in grayscale; bottom images are inverted to provide a contrasting visual perspective (Images copyrighted Jonathan Schwartz; Jean-Phillipe Fontanille; and Vignon P)
Image enhancements and matchmaking provided by A Lerma.

Catalano/Schwartz – Enrie/Schwartz letter mapping

Supplement B-1

Images copyrighted G.M. Catalano; Jonathan Schwartz;
The Enrie image [3rd from top] is sourced from Mario Latendresse and the ShroudScope website.
Image enhancements and matchmaking provided by A Lerma.

Catalano/Schwartz – Enrie/Schwartz letter mapping (inverted)

Supplement B-2

Images copyrighted G.M. Catalano; Jonathan Schwartz;
The Enrie image [3rd from top] is sourced from Mario Latendresse and the ShroudScope website.
Image enhancements and matchmaking provided by A Lerma.

Vignon/Schwartz – Castex/Schwartz letter mapping

Supplement B-3

(Copyrighted Vignon P; Jonathan Schwartzj; and Thierry Castex)
Image enhancements and matchmaking provided by A Lerma.

Vignon/Schwartz – Castex/Schwartz letter mapping (inverted)

Supplement B-4

(Images copyrighted Vignon P; Jonathan Schwartz; and Thierry Castex)
Image enhancements and matchmaking provided by A Lerma.

**Supplement B – Table
Letter mapping observations**

Letter/Notes	Source Image			
	Catalano	Enrie	Vignon	Castex
M	Second peak end points defined on inverted Catalano image	Similar pattern detected @ the second peak	Inconclusive, linen mesh patterns overtake other details	Inconclusive, linen mesh patterns overtake other details
A	Inconclusive	Faint 'A' triangle form	"	"
X	"	Bubble formation @ bottom of 'X' (both images)	"	"
I	"	Inconclusive	"	"
M	Trace lines are defined on inverted Catalano image	Triangle form @ first peak and half-circle @ second peak	"	"
P	Inconclusive	Circular formation appears top left (both images)	"	"
O	"	Dark spot appears where center of 'O' should be	Bubble appears below 'O' (both images)	"
N	Line shadows mimic on inverted Catalano image	Shape of 'J' traceable on the Schwartz image	"	'N' outline observable on original and inverted image
T*	/	/	/	/
I*	/	/	/	/
F*	/	/	/	/

Detectability¹⁸: Further inspection may reveal bubbles or tracings not identified in this table.

* Letters not detectable due to off-center striking.

¹⁸ Subtleties, i.e. shape, shadings, or other characteristics showing similarities in the lettering of the coin and the TS image that suggest a likely 'presence' of that letter within the hash patterns; taking into account that such an image at a higher resolution would expectedly appear more pixelated on an uneven and corrugated surface of linen fibers.

Catalano (top)/Enrie (bottom) defined markings

Supplement C-1

Bell curve

Images copyrighted G.M. Catalano; Jonathan Schwartz;
 The Enrie image [3rd from top] is sourced from Mario Latendresse and the ShroudScope website.
 Image enhancements and matchmaking provided by A Lerma.

Vignon (top)/Fontanille (bottom) defined markings

Supplement C-2

U shape 3

(Copyrighted Vignon P; Jonathan Schwartz; and J-P Fontanille)
Image enhancements and matchmaking provided by A Lerma.

**Supplement C – Table
Pattern¹⁹-type observations within lettering vicinity²⁰**

Source Image	'MAXIM' Designation	'PONTIF' Designation
Catalano	Dotted border; line above the lettering	Bell curve over 'N'; other trace patterns
Enrie	Traceable 'A'; '3' followed by 'A' pattern	'A' pattern over N; line running across 'O'
Vignon	Eagle/wing shape over 'X'	Shape of bowtie above 'O'
Fontanille	Not provided	'A' shape above N; '3' shape inside 'N' box

¹⁹ Not inclusive of all other patterns detectable; other patterns may be observable within lettering vicinity.

²⁰ Other patterns outside lettering vicinity may be observable and numerous to list here.

Schwartz/Catalano checkered overlay

Supplement D-1

(Sources: The Julia coin is courtesy of Jonathan Schwartz; the source image is attributable to G. M. Catalano)
Scaling and matchmaking calculations of the Schwartz and Catalano images are attributable to A Lerma.

Schwartz/Catalano checkered overlay (inverted/grayscale)

Supplement D-2

(Sources: The Julia coin is courtesy of Jonathan Schwartz; the source image is attributable to G. M. Catalano)
Scaling and matchmaking calculations of the Schwartz and Catalano images are attributable to A Lerma.

Schwartz/Enrie checkered overlay

Supplement D-3

(Sources: The Julia coin is courtesy of Jonathan Schwartz; the source image is attributable to Mario Latendresse and ShroudScope.com)

Scaling and matchmaking calculations of the Schwartz and the Enrie images are attributable to A Lerma.

Schwartz/Vignon checked overlay

Supplement D-4

(Sources: The Julia coin is courtesy of Jonathan Schwartz; the source image is attributable to Vignon P)
Scaling and matchmaking calculations of the Schwartz and Vignon images are attributable to A Lerma.

Schwartz/Castex checked overlay

Supplement D-5

(Sources: The Julia coin is courtesy of Jonathan Schwartz; the source image is attributable to Thierry Castex)
Scaling and matchmaking calculations of the Schwartz and Castex images are attributable to A Lerma.

Schwartz/Catalano cross-hash mapping

Supplement E-1

(Sources: The Julia coin is courtesy of Jonathan Schwartz; the source image is attributable to G. M. Catalano)
Scaling and matchmaking calculations of the Schwartz and Catalano images are attributable to A Lerma.

Schwartz/Enrie cross-hash mapping

Supplement E-2

(Sources: The Julia coin is courtesy of Jonathan Schwartz; the source image is attributable to Mario Latendresse and ShroudScope.com)
Scaling and matchmaking calculations of the Schwartz and Enrie images are attributable to A Lerma.

Schwartz/Vignon cross-hash mapping

Supplement E-3

(Sources: The Julia coin is courtesy of Jonathan Schwartz; the source image is attributable to Vignon P)
Scaling and matchmaking calculations of the Schwartz and Vignon images are attributable to A Lerma.

Schwartz/Castex cross-hash mapping

Supplement E-4

(Sources: The Julia coin is courtesy of Jonathan Schwartz; the source image is attributable to Thierry Castex)
Scaling and matchmaking calculations of the Schwartz and Castex images are attributable to A Lerma.

Schwartz/Vignon orientation of linen fiber course

Supplement F

(Sources: The Julia coin is courtesy of Jonathan Schwartz; the image on the right has been cropped from the original. Image credit: HA, taken from the Pinterest website, file name: 4a01ec4370385ea4c29dc6457c17681c.jpg)

Scaling and matchmaking calculations of the Schwartz, Vignon, and HA images are attributable to A Lerma.